

Sex Assessment Using Odontometry and Cranial Anthropometry : Evaluation in North Indian Population

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Introduction

- Determination of sex is an essential parameter which helps in establishing the biological profile of the deceased in forensic and archaeological examinations.
- Esthetics is the primary consideration for patients seeking any prosthetic treatment.
- Dental and cranial parameters can help in biological profiling and sex determination of individuals
- Also has Esthetic Significance

- Proper selection of size and shape of tooth is one of the most important factors contributing to a harmonious esthetics and smile.
- Cranial and odontometric parameters are useful adjuncts in sex determination.
- Considerable dimorphism in males and females.
- They exhibit sexual dimorphism and can be useful in personal profiling, forensic identification and anthropological studies.
- The purpose of this study is Sex assessment using Odontometry and cranial anthropometry in North Indian Population.

Aim of The Study

- To correlate the odontometric measurement of six maxillary anterior teeth with interpupillary distance, intercanine width and head circumference in sex determination in North Indian population.

Objectives

- To compare the mesiodistal width in maxillary anterior teeth with head circumference, interpupillary distance and inter canine width.
- To correlate the odontometric measurements with cranial morphometric measurements.
- To determine the significance of these parameters in sex determination.

Material and Methods

- Cranial anthropometric measurements i.e. maximum head circumference, interpupillary distance and intercanine width were measured.
- Tooth size (maximum mesiodistal dimensions) of six maxillary anterior teeth were measured with digital caliper.
- To ascertain the usefulness of absolute measurements of interpupillary distance, cranial circumference and teeth and the combination of these parameters in sex prediction, Pearson's correlation analysis and Wilcoxon sign rank analysis was done.

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Comparison of Means of Variables in Males and Females in the study groups

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

- **Inclusion Criteria**
 1. No missing maxillary anterior teeth.
 2. No gingival or periodontal conditions or therapies that would undermine a healthy tissue to tooth relationship.
 3. Not undergone any previous dental restorative, esthetic or orthodontic treatment.
 4. All anterior teeth were erupted.
- **Exclusion criteria**
 1. Periodontal disease with interproximal gingival recession greater than 2.0 mm.
 2. Previous history of periodontal surgery.
 3. Subject undergoing orthodontic therapy during study.
 4. Subject with open bite.
 5. Apparent loss of tooth structure due to attrition, fracture, caries or restorations

Statistical Analysis

- Data analyzed by using SPSS software (v.20).
- Student T- test and descriptive statistics applied .
- The independent t-test performed to observe the differences of the ratio of six maxillary anterior teeth between different head circumferences at 95% confidential and $p \leq 0.05$ considered statistically significant.
- Pearson’s correlation coefficient calculated for each parameter.

Independent Sample Student T test , $p \leq 0.05$ considered statistically significant with 95% confidence intervals

Inter and Intra Group Comparison

Parameters		Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Head Circumference	Between Groups	1883.56	1883.56	40.449	≤ 0.05
	Within Groups	4563.48	46.566		
	Total	6447.04			
Inter Pupillary distance	Between Groups	558.85	558.85	30.856	≤ 0.05
	Within Groups	1774.908	18.111		
	Total	2333.758			
Inter canine distance	Between Groups	75.169	75.169	4.225	≤ 0.05
	Within Groups	1743.513	17.791		
	Total	1818.682			

ANOVA test, $p \leq 0.05$ considered statistically significant with 95% confidence intervals

Inter and Intra Group Comparison

Parameters		Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F	Sig.
RCI	Between Groups	13.764	13.764	34.145	0
	Within Groups	39.505	0.403		
	Total	53.269			
LCI	Between Groups	4.796	4.796	7.035	0.009
	Within Groups	66.811	0.682		
	Total	71.608			
RLI	Between Groups	3.891	3.891	5.92	0.017
	Within Groups	63.761	0.657		
	Total	67.652			
LLI	Between Groups	0.008	0.008	0.016	0.899
	Within Groups	49.19	0.502		
	Total	49.198			
RC	Between Groups	31.81	31.81	0.576	0.45
	Within Groups	5415.238	55.258		
	Total	5447.048			
LC	Between Groups	4.641	4.641	10.148	0.002
	Within Groups	44.362	0.457		
	Total	49.003			
SUM	Between Groups	99.202	99.202	1.363	0.246
	Within Groups	7133.758	72.793		
	Total	7232.96			

ANOVA test, $p \leq 0.05$ considered statistically significant with 95% confidence intervals

Correlation Coefficient of Dental and Craniofacial parameters in the study groups

Pearson Correlation Coefficient, $p \leq 0.05$ considered statistically significant with 95% confidence intervals

Discussion

- The estimation of sex from osteological and dental records has long been an interdisciplinary field of dentistry, forensic medicine and anthropology.
- Forensic tools for dental sex determination can broadly be categorised into metric, non-metric, and biochemical methods.
- The cranial and odontological sex estimation methods are highly population-specific and there is a great need for these methods to be applied to and verified on more populations.
- This study analyzed the clinical crown dimensions of maxillary anterior teeth to determine whether consistent relationships exist between tooth width and several cranial measur-

ements in a subset of the North Indian population.

- In the present study, there was significant difference in the odontometric measurements in males and females.
- Jatana et al. (2022) observed that maxillary canines had strong sexual dimorphism and can be utilised for sex determination in Punjab population.
- Proportional relationships between the bizygomatic width and the width of the central incisor, and the intercanine distance and the interalar width in women were observed by Hasanreisgolu et al. (2015).
- Jamayat et al. (2014) observed that mesiodistal crown width and lengths correlated with facial types in Bangladeshi population.
- The odontometric difference between males and females is generally explained as a result of greater genetic expression in males.
- However, Iscan and Kedici (2003) cautioned that an overlap exists between male and female tooth dimensions, and this makes accurate diagnosis of sex challenging, even for experienced dentists. They emphasized that success is greater when all available teeth are used.

Conclusion

- There exists significant differences between tooth-mesiodistal width and head circumference dimensions, intercanine width and interpupillary width in study population.
- The craniometric and odontometric measurements are useful adjunctive tools in sex determination and forensic identification in North Indian population.
- This can also help in selection of missing anterior teeth as per individual esthetic and restorative requirements based on cranial and anatomical morphometric measurements.